

POROSITY CALCULATION OF MIXTURES OF FIBROUS PARTICLES

R. P. Zou ¹, A. B. Yu ¹, and D. L. Xu ²

¹ *School of Materials Science and Engineering, The University of New South Wales
Sydney, NSW 2052, Australia*

² *Department of Materials Engineering, Xi'an University of Architecture and Technology
Xi'an 710055, P. R. China*

SUMMARY: The initial forming of fibre blend to high green density, i.e. the packing of fibrous particles, is important to the reinforcement of composite materials. It is very useful to develop a general predictive method for the optimum selection of particle mixtures for the property control of ceramic or composite products. This paper presents such a mathematical model developed on the basis of the similarity analysis between the spherical and non-spherical particle packings and assesses its applicability to the packing of fibrous particles with discrete and/or continuous length distributions. The results indicate that the model can predict this packing system well and hence provides an effective way to solve various packing problems in the composite materials processing.

KEYWORDS: packing, porosity calculation, fibrous particles, mixtures

INTRODUCTION

Among the many variables governing the packing of particles, particle size distribution is most important. Many efforts have therefore been made to understand the relationship between packing density (equal to one minus porosity) and particle size distribution, as summarised by German [1]. Generally speaking, previous work is mainly based on experimental measurement and recent studies are more concerned with mathematical modelling. In the past decade or so, significant progress has been made in the modelling of the packing of spherical particles [2-7]. The resulting mathematical models have significantly enhanced our quantitative understanding of the dependence of packing density on particle size distribution and provide an effective means for solving various packing problems. However, particles involved in practice are usually not spherical, and particle shape strongly affects particle packing. In the past, little systematic effort has been made to model the packing of nonspherical particles, mainly because of the complexity of the problem. Recently, to overcome this gap, on the basis of the similarity analysis between spherical and non-spherical particle packings, a mathematical model has been developed for predicting the packing of non-spherical particle mixtures [8].

Of particular interest here is the packing of fibrous particles. It has been known that the reinforcement of ceramic or composite materials using high strength fibres can yield high temperature structural materials with increased toughness. Understanding the initial forming of fibre blend to high green density is important to the involved processes. The packing of fibres or fibrous particles has therefore been a subject of research for years, aiming at

developing a predictive method for the optimum selection of particle mixtures for the property control of ceramic or composite products. Simple packing systems, involving mono-sized or fibre-fibre or sphere-fibre binary mixtures, have been studied in detail [9-14]. In contrast, to date very limited efforts have been given to complicated but more realistic packing systems involving multi-sized fibres [15,16].

This paper will present a study of the packing of fibrous particles by use of the modified linear packing model [8]. In particular, its applicability to the packing systems encountered in the composite materials processing will be assessed in detail. It will be shown that the model can predict the packing of these systems well and hence provides a convenient way to study the packing of fibrous particles.

THEORETICAL WORK

Mathematical Model

The system considered is assumed to be composed of n components of constant particle density, with each characterised by its (initial) porosity ϵ_i and effective (packing) diameter d_{pi} ($i=1, 2, \dots, n$). In general, the porosity of this system ϵ can be expressed as

$$\epsilon=f(X_1, X_2, \dots, X_n, d_{p1}, d_{p2}, \dots, d_{pn}, \epsilon_1, \epsilon_2, \dots, \epsilon_n) \tag{1}$$

where X_i is the fractional solid volume of the i th component. For convenience, d_{pi} are so ordered that $d_{p1} \geq d_{p2} \geq \dots \geq d_{pn}$.

Fig. 1: A two-dimensional diagram illustrating a packing of non-spherical particles and its equivalent packing of spherical particles.

Eqn 1 implies that the particle characteristics, such as size and shape, affects the packing porosity through its effect on equivalent packing diameter and initial porosity. When particles of different sizes are mixed and packed, the volume occupied by a unit volume of solid particles, commonly referred to as the specific volume V [$=1/(1-\epsilon)$], will decrease as compared with that of mono-sized particles as a result of the mixing-interaction between two components. It is known that the mixing-interaction between two components is dependent on

their relative size which, as discussed elsewhere [17], should be quantified in terms of equivalent packing diameter resulting from the similarity analysis between spherical and non-spherical particle packings. This concept is schematically illustrated in Fig. 1 in which a packing of non-spherical particles is represented by its corresponding packing of spheres.

Technically speaking, knowing X_i , d_{pi} and ϵ_i allows ϵ to be predicted by means of a mathematical model which calculates porosity based on the same information. However, if there is a significant difference in initial porosity, the situation often found in the packing of non-spherical particles, the previous models [2-7] can not be satisfactorily used. The only model that can overcome this deficiency is the modified linear packing model. Yu et al. [8] have described this model in detail. The following just lists the model equations for porosity calculation.

According to the modified linear packing model, specific volume V can be determined by the following equations [8]:

$$V = \text{Max.} \{V_1^T, V_2^T, \dots, V_n^T\} \quad (2a)$$

where

$$V_i^T = \sum_{j=1}^{i-1} [V_j - (V_j - 1)g(r_{ij})]X_j + V_i X_i + \sum_{j=i+1}^n V_j [1 - f(r_{ij})]X_j \quad (2b)$$

where V_i are the initial specific volumes which can be determined from ϵ_i by definition. Eqn 2a means that V equals the maximum of v_i^T ($i=1, 2, \dots, n$). $f(r_{ij})$ and $g(r_{ij})$ are referred to as the interaction functions and only dependent on r_{ij} , the small-to-large ratio of equivalent packing diameters between components i and j , and can be determined as

$$f(r_{ij}) = (1 - r_{ij})^{3.33} + 2.81r_{ij}(1 - r_{ij})^{2.77} \quad (3)$$

and

$$g(r_{ij}) = (1 - r_{ij})^{1.97} + 0.36r_{ij}(1 - r_{ij})^{3.67} \quad (4)$$

Packing Characteristics of Mono-sized Fibres

Use of the above equations in porosity calculation requires the information of packing characteristics such as ϵ_i and d_{pi} a priori. It has been established that initial porosity is constant for coarse spherical particles, generally taking the value of 0.4 for the loose random packing or 0.36 for the dense random packing [1]. However, initial porosity varies with particle shape and, if particle size is smaller than a certain value, particle size as well. If the particle size and shape of component i are, respectively, represented by its equivalent volume diameter d_{vi} and sphericity ψ_i , this gives

$$\epsilon_i = f(d_{vi}, \psi_i) \quad (5)$$

Similar arguments apply to effective diameter d_{pi} , so that

$$d_{pi} = f(d_{vi}, \psi_i) \quad (6)$$

The effect of particle size becomes important when the weak forces such as van der Waals and electrostatic forces are dominant, which will give packing behaviour different from that of coarse particles [1,18]. However, the use of a mechanic force, eg tapping/vibration or compaction, will significantly reduce this effect and give a packing matching the packing of coarse particles. In this case, the effect of particle size can be ignored. The present work only deals with such packing systems.

The packing characteristics of mono-sized non-spherical particles has been studied by Zou and Yu [19]. Fig. 2 shows their measured porosity results as a function of aspect ratio L_i (length to diameter) for fibrous particles, which can be fitted by the following equation:

$$\ln \varepsilon_i = \psi_i^{5.58} \times \exp[5.89 \times (1 - \psi_i)] \times \ln 0.40 \quad (7a)$$

for the loose random packing, and

$$\ln \varepsilon_i = \psi_i^{6.74} \times \exp[8.00 \times (1 - \psi_i)] \times \ln 0.36 \quad (7b)$$

for the dense random packing; where ψ_i depends on L_i , given by

$$\psi_i = \frac{2.621L_i^{2/3}}{1 + 2L_i} \quad (8)$$

Different experimental conditions may change Eqn 7, which in turn affects porosity. On the other hand, for a given packing system, ε_i or V_i can be readily measured, and these measured values can be used directly in a model calculation, which usually improves the prediction accuracy. In fact, this treatment has been used for most of the application examples presented in this paper.

Fig 2: Initial porosity vs. particle shape for fibrous particles

The similarity between spherical and non-spherical particle packings has led to the development of the concept of equivalent packing diameter. In particular, for convex non-

spherical particles, the dependence of d_{pi} on ψ_i has been empirically established, given by [19]

$$d_{vi}/d_{pi} = \psi_i^{2.785} \times \exp[2.946(1 - \psi_i)] \quad (9)$$

By definition, d_{vi} should be related to the diameter of a fibrous particle D_i , in addition to its aspect ratio, as given by

$$d_{vi} = 1.145 L_i^{1/3} D_i \quad (10)$$

Incorporation of Eqns 7-10 into the above model allows the packing porosity of a mixture of fibrous particles to be predicted. Its accuracy will be discussed in the section below.

MODEL VALIDATION

The validity of the modified linear model can be examined by comparing the calculated and measured porosity results. For convenience, this comparison is here made for three cases: (1) the packing of fibres with a discrete length distribution; (2) the packing of fibres with a continuous length distribution; and (3) the packing of mixtures of fibres and other shaped particles.

Packing of Fibres with a Discrete Length Distribution

The first example considered here is the binary packing of fibrous particles. Milewski [9] has carried out a detailed study of this system. Fig. 3 shows one set of his measured results, and the predictions. It is obvious that the predictions are in good agreement with the measurements. Such good agreement can also be observed for the packing of multi-component mixtures. As an example, Fig. 4 shows the results for a quaternary system recently studied by Lin [20]. Note that the results are presented in triangular diagrams by fixing the fractional solid volume of a component at pre-set values, this giving the so-called pseudo-ternary packings.

Fig. 3 Porosity results of binary mixtures of short ($L=3.91$) and long fibres of different L values, $D=2.09$ mm for all fibres: points, measurements; solid lines, predictions.

Fig. 4 Comparison between the measured and calculated packing density, ie. 1-porosity, for a quaternary system of fibrous particle of sizes: $D=2.62$ mm, $L_1=45.0$, $L_2=15.9$, $L_3=3.9$ and $L_4=1.4$ when: (a), $X_3=0$; (b), $X_3=0.20$; (c), $X_2=0.50$.

Packing of Fibres with a Continuous Length Distribution

Practical problems often involve the packing of fibrous particles with a length distribution. This packing system was recently experimentally studied by Zou et al. [16]. In particular, in their study, the fibres were assumed to be of the same diameter D , with their dimensionless lengths, ie, aspect ratios, distributed according to the modified power law length distribution:

$$f_v(L) = \frac{mL^{m-1}}{L_{\max}^m - L_{\min}^m} \quad (L_{\min} \leq L \leq L_{\max}) \quad (11)$$

or the log-normal length distribution:

$$f_v(L) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi}} \times \frac{1}{L} \times \frac{1}{\ln \sigma_g} \times \exp \left[-\frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\ln L - \ln L_{0.5}}{\ln \sigma_g} \right)^2 \right] \quad (12)$$

Eqn 11 is similar to the modified Gaudin-Schuhman distribution using particle diameter rather than length. Obviously, for a given D , porosity should be dependent on the length range, i.e. $[L_{\min}, L_{\max}]$, and exponent m . On the other hand, for Eqn 12, porosity depends on median length $L_{0.5}$ and geometric standard variation σ_g . Zou et al. [16] found that: porosity increases with the increase of m or length range for Eqn 11, or with the increase of $L_{0.5}$ or σ_g for Eqn 12. Figs. 5 and 6 show their experimental results, together with the model predictions obtained under their experimental conditions. The good agreement between predicted and measured porosities suggests that this packing system can be well predicted by the proposed model.

Fig. 5 Porosity of cylinders with the modified powder law length distribution for various length ranges for the loose random packing: points, measurements; —, predictions.

Fig. 6 Porosity of fibrous particles with the log-normal length distribution under various conditions: (a), $\sigma_g = 3.5$; (b), $L_{0.5} = 8.0$; points, measurements; —, predictions.

Fig. 7 Comparison between the measured (a) and calculated (b) specific volume variations for a disk-cylinder-sphere ternary system: disk, $d_{p1} = 20.59$ mm, $V_1 = 2.653$; cylinder, $d_{p2} = 10.95$ mm, $V_2 = 2.155$; sphere, $d_{p3} = 3.00$ mm, $V_3 = 1.639$.

Packing of Mixtures of Fibres and Other Shaped Particles

The proposed model may be used for predicting the porosity of non-spherical particle mixtures which include mixtures of fibres and other shaped particles, as long as ϵ_i and d_{pi} have been properly evaluated. This can be seen from the example given below.

The packing of ternary mixtures of non-spherical particles has been experimentally studied by Yu et al [15] using well defined particles such as disk and/or cylinders. To depict the similarity between spherical and non-spherical particle packings, these authors used the so-called specific volume variation ΔV in their analysis, which is defined as the difference in specific volume between unmixed and mixed states. That is

$$\Delta V = \sum_{i=1}^n V_i - V \quad (13)$$

The so-called mixed state corresponds to the present V , and the unmixed state the specific volume obtained when different types of particles are placed layer by layer without mixing. As shown in Fig. 7, their measurements can be predicted by the proposed model satisfactorily.

CONCLUSIONS

Fibrous particles are widely used in composite materials manufacturing. However, various industrial needs require various mixtures, which give various packing features as seen from the results presented in this paper. Development of a predictive method for the optimum control of such mixtures has been an important research subject. In this paper, extensive examination has been made of the application of the modified linear packing model of Yu et al. [8] to the packing of fibrous particles. The results indicate that the model can predict this packing system well and hence provides a convenient and cost-effective way to solve various packing problems.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

This work is partially supported by Australian Research Council (ARC), Energy and Research Development Corporation (ERDC) and Department of Industry, Science and Tourism (DIST).

REFERENCES

1. German, R. M., Particle Packing Characteristics, Metal Powder Industries Federation, Princeton, New Jersey, 1989.
2. Dodds, J. A., "The Porosity and Contact Points in Multicomponent Random Sphere Packing Calculated By a Simple Statistical Geometric Model," J. Colloid Interface Sci., Vol. 77, 1980, pp. 317-327.
3. Ouchiya, N. and Tanaka, T., "Porosity Estimation from Particle Size Distribution," Ind. Eng. Chem. Fundam., Vol. 25, 1986, pp. 125-129.
4. Stovall, T., De Larrard, F. and Buil, M., "Linear Packing Density Model of Grain Mixtures," Powder Technol., Vol. 48, 1986, pp. 1-12.

5. Marshall, J. S. and Dhir, V. K., "On the Prediction of Porosity of Beds Composed of Mixtures of Spherical Particles," *Chem. Eng. Commun.*, Vol. 48, 1986, pp. 261-285.
6. Yu A. B. and Standish, N., "An Analytical-Parametric Theory of the Random Packing of Particles," *Powder Technol.*, Vol. 55, 1988, pp. 171-186.
7. Yu A. B. and Standish, N., "Estimation of the Porosity of Particle Mixtures by a Linear-Mixture Packing Model," *Ind. Eng. Chem. Res.*, Vol. 30, 1991, pp. 1372-1385.
8. Yu, A. B., Zou, R. P. and Standish, N., "Modifying the linear packing model for predicting the porosity of non-spherical particle mixtures," *Ind. Eng. Chem. Res.*, Vol. 35, 1996, pp. 3730-3741.
9. Milewski, J. V., "The Combined Packing of Rods and Spheres in Reinforcing Plastics," *Ind. Eng. Chem. Prod. Res. Dev.*, 17, 363-366 (1978).
10. Starr, T. L., "Packing Density of Fiber/Powder Blends". *Am. Ceram. Soc. Bull.*, Vol. 65, 1986, pp. 1293-1296.
11. Evans, K. E. and Gibson, A. G., "Prediction of the maximum packing fraction achievable in randomly oriented short-fibre composites", *Composites Sci. and Tech.*, Vol. 25, 1986, pp. 149-162.
12. Milewski, J. V., "Packing Concepts in the Utilisation of Filler and Reinforcement Combinations", *Handbook of Fillers and Reinforcements for Plastics*, Milewski, J. V. and Katz, H. S., Eds., Van Nostrand Reinhold, New York, 1987, pp. 14-33.
13. Evans, K. E. and Ferrar, M. D., *J. Phys. D.* 22 (1989) 354.
14. Yu, A. B., Standish, N. and McLean, A., "Porosity Calculation of Binary Mixtures of Nonspherical Particles", *J. Am. Ceram. Soc.*, Vol. 76, 1993, pp. 2813-2816.
15. Yu, A. B., Zou, R. P. and Standish, N., "The Packing of Ternary Mixtures of Non-Spherical Particles", *J. Am. Ceram. Soc.*, Vol. 75, 1992, pp. 2765-2772.
16. Zou, R. P., Lin, Y. X., Yu, A. B. and Wong, P., "The packing of cylindrical particles with a length distribution," *Am. Ceram. Soc.*, 1996 (in press).
17. Yu, A. B. and Standish, N. "Characterisation of Non-Spherical Particles from Their Packing Behaviour," *Powder Technol.*, Vol. 74, 1993, pp. 205-213.
18. Yu, A. B., Bridgwater, J. and Burbidge, A., "On the modelling of the packing of fine particles", *Powder Technol.*, 1997 (in press).
19. Zou, R. P. and Yu, A. B., "Evaluation of the packing characteristics of monosized non-spherical particles", *Powder Technol.*, Vol. 88, 1996, pp. 71-79.
20. Lin, Y. X., "*The Packing of Fibrous Particles*", M. Appl. Sci. Thesis, Univ. of NSW, Feb. 1996.